

Comparative Relationship between Parental Involvement and Academic Engagement among Secondary School Students in Delta State Nigeria.

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Abstract

The study sought to investigate the comparative relationship between parental involvement and students' academic engagement among secondary school students in Delta State Nigeria. Two research questions and two null hypotheses guided the study. The study adopted correlation research design. The population of the study consists of 41744 (Male 20365, and Female, 21379) senior secondary school class two (SS2) students during the 2023/2024 academic session in Delta State, and the sample size was 769 (Male, 384 and Female, 385) SS2 students drawn from the target population using multi stage sampling technique. Two instruments namely: Parental Involvement Questionnaire (PIQ) and Academic Engagement Questionnaire (AEQ) were used for data collection. The instruments were validated by three experts from the Faculty of Education, Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka. Reliability indices of 0.87 and 0.92, respectively were obtained for the instruments. Data collected were analyzed using coefficient of determination to answer the research questions, while the multiple regression analysis was employed to test the null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The findings of the study revealed a positive relationship between parental involvement and academic engagement among secondary school students in Delta State. Based on the findings of the study, it was concluded that parental involvement significantly correlated positively with secondary school students academic engagement. It was however, recommended among others that parents should create adequate time and be encouraged to be involved in their children education so that students can be focused in meaningful academic engagement.

Keywords: Relationship, Parental involvement, Students Engagement

Introduction

In Nigeria, education remains the largest industry and government continues to ensure that funds, instructional material and teaching personnel and made available for the sector (Ade, 2014). Good education does not happen by chance and secondary schools are critical to students' academic success and overall educational outcomes. Student engagement becomes a critical success factor (CSF) that has emerged to determine students' experiences and academic achievements. According to Bryson (2014), student engagement in secondary schools is consistently emphasized in research, refers student engagement to which student are actively involved, motivated, and committed to their learning process and school activities. Academically engaged students, consistently out perform their less engaged students, reaching their full potential and achieving greater levels of success (Juvonen and Kinfsend, 2016).

Khan, Egbue, Palkie and Madden (2017) asserted that highly engaged students demonstrate a more in-depth understanding of the subject matter, actively participate in classroom discussions, and willing to ask participation benefits not only themselves but also their active participation benefits only themselves but also their follow students, contributing to a dynamic and stimulating classroom environment. Student engagement has significant impact on students' social-emotional well-being (Heffner and Anataramian, 2016). Museus, Yi and Saelua (2017) asserted that engaged students have a stronger sense of belonging, connection, and positive relationship in their school community. They have a higher chance of developing healthy self-esteem, confidence, and resilience (Bouden, Tickle and Naumann, 2021; Gao, Mei and Guo, 2020). (Yang, Liu, Li and Li, 2022), emphasized that students who are engaged report lower levels of stress and anxiety because they perceive school to be a supportive and nurturing environment.

Furthermore, student engagement is important in determining students' long-term educational and career outcomes. Engaged students are more likely to pursue higher education, develop career goals and develop the skills and competencies required for future success. They demonstrate greater motivation and self-regulation, both of which are necessary for lifelong learning and personal growth (Holec and Marynowski, 2020).

Disengagement of students in Delta state is a problem as evidenced by lack of interest in class activities or assignments, difficulty participating in class, difficulty staying on task, disconnection from peers, teachers and parents, inattentiveness or lack of focus during class, that lead to the high number of out-of-school children. According to Nigeria Multidimensional Poverty Index NMPI (2022), Delta state has approximately 140,000 out-of-school children between the ages of 6 and 15, which accounts for 9.30% of the population. This figure is alarming considering an oil rich state like Delta. According to Gairin, Triado, Feixas, Figuera, Aparicio-Chueca and Torrado (2014), when students are disengaged from their education, it hinders that motivation, interest, and commitment to the learning process and school activities. Amenah, (2019) emphasized the decline in interest and poor academic achievement among secondary school student in Delta State, indicating the negative consequences of disengagement. This lack of engagement ultimately leads to poor performance, limited understanding of subject matter, and reduced participation in classroom discussions.

Recent research suggests that there are multiple factors that influence school engagement. These factors include effective communication, collaboration, active involvement in learning activities, enriching educational experiences, positive interactions between students and teachers, appropriate academic challenges, supportive classroom and family environments, availability of resources, parental involvement, and interest in a child's learning material (Araque et al., 2017; Clark, 2015, Furrer et al., 2014; Kim et al; 2019; Kutsyuruba et al., 2015; Lee, 2014; Pellas, 2014; SalmelaAro and Upadyaya, 2014; Wang and Fredricks, 2014; Whytesell, 2016). Among these factors, the article will specifically investigate the comparative relationship between parental involvement and academic engagement among secondary school students in Delta State.

Parental involvement is an important factor in influencing student engagement and academic outcomes. When parents actively participate in their children's education, it improves their academic performance and overall well-being (Upadyaya and Salmela-Aro 2013). Parental involvement is defined as active participation in their children's educational journey, which includes various forms of support communication, and collaboration between, parents and schools (Kwan and Wong, 2016). Research consistently shows that parental involvement has a positive impact on students' academic achievement, motivation, and overall school success (Anthony and Ogg, 2019; Boonk, Gijsselaers, Ritzen and Brand-Gruwel, 2018; Jsiswal and Choudhuri, 2017; Mahuro and Hungi, 2016).

The establishment of a strong home-school partnership is an important aspect of parental involvement (Okeke, 2014). Students benefit from a cohesive support system that extends beyond the classroom when parents and schools collaborate. Actively involved parents in their children education show a vested interest in their academic progress and well-being, which foster a positive learning environment (Darling-Hammond and Cook-Havey, 2018). Attending parent teacher conferences, participating in school events, volunteering, assisting with homework, and engaging in regular communication with teachers are all examples of parental involvement (Kimaro and Machumu, 2015). These activities show students that their education is important not only of school, but also at home, reinforcing a sense of importance and commitment to their education.

Several positive outcomes emerge when parents participate in their children's education. Parental involvement raises students' motivation and self-assurance. Students feel supported and encouraged by their parents increase their confidence and sense of self-efficacy (Alacam, 2015). As a result, students are more engaged in classroom activities and more willing to take on academic challenges. Parental involvement helps to improve academic performance. Parents who actively participate in their children's education can provide additional guidance, monitor progress, and offer support as needed (mahuro and Hungi; 2016). This additional supports system emphasizes the value of education and assists students in staying on track, resulting in improved grades and overall academic performance.

Furthermore, Afolabi, (2014) asserted that parental involvement promotes improved communication between home and school. It also enables parents to stay up to date on their children progress and actively participate in discussions about their academic and personal development. However, it is critical to recognize that parental involvement should be inclusive and take into account different family structures, cultural backgrounds, and socioeconomic circumstances (Murray, Mcfarland-Piazza and Harrison, 2015). Schools should strive to create and inclusive environment that encourages and accommodates parental involvement regardless of individual

circumstances. By conducting this research within Delta State, it presents an opportunity to explore this variable that shape the interaction and the impact on students' engagement.

The major problem to be addressed by this research is student's engagement. In secondary schools in Delta state, student disengagement poses a significant challenge, evident in inattentiveness, or lack of focus during class, disinterest in class activities or assignments, avoiding class, or not completing homework, disconnection from peers, teachers and parents that lead to high number of out-of-school children and poor academic performance. A good number of parents give little attention to the academic work of their children.

The Nigeria Multidimensional Poverty Index (NMPI) (2022) shows that Delta State has approximately 14,000 out-of-school children between ages 6 and 15, which accounts for 9.30% of the population. This figure is alarming for an oil-rich state like Delta. Poor parenting at home, lack of parent involvement in parent child discussion on academic issues, stress on the part of parent ability to solve problems probably not knowledgeable enough contribute to students' disengagement. These have negatively affected the child's ability to get engaged in learning. One of such consequence is evident in the poor performance of the student both in internal and external examination. Through observation students behavior show that most students parents are not involve in supporting their children to guide them through life so as to achieve their goals

Lack of comprehensive understanding of how parental involvement influences students engagement hinders the ability to develop evidence-based policies and initiatives that promote positive educational outcomes. As a result students may continue to experience decreased motivation, limited participation and reduced academic achievement. By conducting this research, this study aims to provide valuable insights and evidence-based recommendations that can inform the development of effective interventions and educational policies, ultimately fostering a supportive and engaging learning environment for students in Delta State.

Objectives of the Study

The objective of the study was to investigate the relationship between parental involvement and student academic engagement among Senior Secondary Schools. Specifically, the study aims to:

1. Assess the relationship between parental involvement and student academic engagement among secondary school students in Delta State.
2. Determine the nature of the regression for predicting student academic engagement based on the variable parental involvement among secondary schools students in Delta State.

Research Questions

The following research question guided the study:

1. What is the relationship between parental involvement and student academic engagement among Secondary Schools students in Delta State?
2. What is the nature of the regression model for predicting academic engagement based on the variable parental involvement among secondary school students in Delta State?

Hypothesis

1. There is no significant relationship between parental involvement and academic engagement among Secondary School students in Delta State.
2. The regression model based on the variable parental involvement does not significantly predict academic engagement among secondary school students in Delta State.

Methodology

The study employed a correlation survey research design. According to Nworgu (2015), correlation survey research design seeks to establish whet relationship exist between two or more variables, using statistics known as correlation co-efficient.

A correlation survey is preferred in this study because it gets at the degree of association rather than merely try to find whether the effect is present or absent. It indicates the direction and magnitude of the relationship existing between parental involvement and student engagement of Secondary School in Delta State, without the manipulation of the independent variable. The public Senior Secondary School (SS2) students were used for the study. The total number of public secondary schools in Delta State was 466. The population of the study consists of 41744 (Male, 20365 and Female, 21379) senior secondary school class two (SS2) students during the 2023/2024 academic session

in Delta State, and the sample size was 769 (Male, 384 and Female, 385) SS2 students drawn from the target population using multi stage sampling technique.

Two instruments were used in this study to collect data. Parental involvement questionnaire (PIQ) and academic engagement questionnaire (AEQ). Two clusters of thirty – one (31) question items. The first cluster investigated the level of parental involvement. The second cluster investigated the academic engagement of students. The two instruments were validated by three experts from the faculty of Education, Nnamdi Azikiwe University Awka. Two of the specialized in Educational Psychology, while the third expert specialized in Measurement and Evaluation.

Data were presented using the simple correlation coefficient and coefficients of determination was used to answer the research questions while the multiple regression analyses was employed to test the null hypotheses at a significance level of 0.05.

Results

Research Question 1:

What is the relationship between parental involvement and student academic engagement among secondary school students in Delta State?

Table 1: Relationship between Parental Involvement and Students' Academic Engagement

Variable	<i>N</i>	Student Academic Engagement	α -level	t(r)-cal	p-val	Decision
Parental Involvement	769	.432	0.05	13.233	.000	Significant relationship

Table 1 shows the relationship between parental academic involvement and students' academic engagement. Using Pearson Product Moment Correlation coefficient, results indicated that there is a moderate positive relationship between parental academic involvement and students' academic engagement.

Research Question 2:

What is the nature of the regression model for predicting academic engagement among secondary schools students in Delta State?

Table 2: Test of significant Relationship between Parental Involvement and Students Academic Engagement.

Variable	<i>N</i>	Student Academic Engagement	α -level	t(r)-cal	p-val	Decision
Parental Involvement	769	.432	0.05	13.233	.000	Significant relationship

Further analysis indicated that there is a statistical significant relationship between parental academic involvement and students' academic engagement. This is so because the *p*-value = .000 is greater than the level of significance = 0.05. Therefore the null hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between parental academic involvement and students' academic engagement is rejected.

Hypothesis 1:

There is no significant relationship between parental involvements and academic engagement among secondary school students in Delta State.

Table 3: Regression Analysis on the Relationship between Parental Academic Involvement and Students Academic Engagement

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	21.900	1.049		20.879	.000

par involvement	.521	.039	.432	13.233	.000
<i>R</i>	.432				
<i>R</i> ²	.186				
<i>F</i>	175.104				.000

a. Dependent Variable: academic engagement

Table 3 showed that regression coefficient *R* was .432 while *R*² was .186. This shows that the predictor variable contributed 18.6% to explain the variances in academic engagement. The corresponding *F* (1, 766) = 175.104, is statistically significant (*p*<.05). Hence, parental academic involvement is a significant predictor of students' academic engagement.

Hypothesis 2:

The regression model based on the variable parental involvement does not significantly predict academic engagement among secondary school students in Delta State

Table 4: Predictive Value of the Independent Variable.

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Coefficients		
1	(Constant)	21.900	1.049		20.879	.000
	par involvement	.489	.040	.405	12..334	.000
	<i>R</i>	.432				
	<i>R</i> ²	.186				
	<i>F</i>	175.104				.000

a. Dependent Variable: academic engagement

Table 4 above showed that parental involvement had a positive significant predictive value on students' academic engagement (B= .405, t= 12.334, *p*<.05. Therefore, parental involvement is a significant predictor of academic engagement of secondary schools students in Delta State.

Discussion of Results

The findings of this study reveal that there is a moderate positive relationship between parental academic involvement and students' academic engagement. Further analysis indicated that there is statistical significant relationship between parental academic involvement and student's engagement and that it is a significant predictor of student's engagement. This finding is in harmony with the findings of (Anthony and Ogg 2019; Boonk, Gijsselaers, Ritzen and Brand-Gruwel, 2016; Jaiswal and Choudhuri, 2017; Mahuro and Hungi, 2016) that parental involvement has a positive impact on students' academic achievement, motivation, engagement and overall school success. This means that the prevailing family Psychodynamics exerted influence on the child determine the direction of correlation, that when parents support their children academics both affectively and cognitively, it becomes obvious that the students' academic engagement will be enhanced. Again, the result of the study further revealed that 18.6 percent variation in students' academic engagement can be attributed to parental academic involvement in their children's education, hence, parental involvement is a significant predictor of students' academic engagement.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of the study, it is concluded that parental involvement significantly correlated positively with secondary school students' academic engagement. This greatly implies that if parents get involved in their children's academic engagement, students will greatly excel in their overall success in their education which can eliminate the problem of student's disengagement in secondary schools in Delta State.

Recommendation

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Parents should create adequate time for their children's education especially in engaging students in their homework, projects and assignments so that students can have meaningful engagement in their studies.

2. School authorities should organize workshops through Parents-Teachers association to enlighten parents on the importance of engagement so that academic disengagement can be minimized or totally eliminated in secondary schools in Delta State.
3. Students should be enlightened by teachers how to be fully engaged in their academics so that they can be focused and excel in their future endeavor.
4. School guidance and counselors should intensify effort to organize seminars for students on the importance of student's engagement and enlighten stakeholders on the disadvantages of students being disengaged from their studies.

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